

Exploring the Area of Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract:

Artificial intelligence is another branch of computer science which aims to develop the machine with human alike intelligence. Artificial intelligence is also has a short name as AI. Artificial intelligence field was founded to mimic the central property of human being that is intelligence. The objective of the artificial intelligence is to simulate human alike properties efficiently and effectively. This has caused to raise philosophical issues about the nature of human mind and its limitations. AI is the subject of optimism, but it has also suffered some setbacks and, today, in 21st Century Artificial intelligence technology has become an essential part of the technological industries by providing the Solutions for the most of the difficult problems in computer science.

Artificial Intelligence has been used and integrated in a different fields like Medical field, Stock exchange, Robotics, scientific discovery and Children's toys. However, many AI applications are not categorized into general applications. But main objective is to incorporate AI technology into general purpose.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is a part of computing science that focuses on creating intelligent machines and programs. The purpose of artificial intelligence is to try to mimic human consciousness and perform tasks such as human beings. In practice it means the ability of a machine or program to think and learn. Generally, the term artificial intelligence means a machine or program that tries to emulate human consciousness. It is claimed that artificial intelligence is playing an increasing role in the research of management science and operational research areas. Intelligence is commonly considered as the ability to collect knowledge and reason about knowledge to solve complex problems.

In the near Future intelligent machines will replace human capabilities in many areas. Artificial intelligence has the advantages over the natural intelligence as it is more permanent, consistent, less expensive, has the ease of duplication and dissemination, can be documented and can perform certain tasks much faster and better than the human. Artificial intelligence refers to the potential of computer controlled machines/robots towards performing tasks that

that almost or similar to human beings. In this case, Artificial intelligence is used to develop various robots that have human intellectual characteristics, behaviours, learning from past experience, have abilities to sense, and abilities to making predications and determine meaning of certain situation.

Robotic technology is largely trending in the present life which has gained popularity in various fields like various industries, hospitals, schools, military, music, gaming, and many others. Artificial Intelligence is an efficient means that make computers and software control robotic thinking with expert systems that significantly illustrate the intelligent behaviour, learning and effectively advice users. In general, Artificial Intelligence is basically known as the ability or potential of robotics to decide, solve problems and reason without much human intervention. There are various innovations of Artificial Intelligence, One such example is robotic cars which doesn't require a driver to control or supervise them. In addition, artificially intelligent technology (robots) involves smart machines that process a large amount of data that a human being can't be in position to perform. [1]

Stages of Artificial Intelligence

- Neural Networks
- Machine Learning and
- Deep Learning

Neural Networks

A neural network is a form of machine learning which is made up of interconnected units that processes information by responding to external inputs, it depends on information between each of the units which are present. The process requires multiple passes of the data so that it can get connections and derive the meaning from undefined data which are been given at present.

Machine Learning

Machine learning automates analytical model building and it also uses different methods such as; Neural networks, operations research, statistics and physics to find undisclosed insights in data without decidedly being shown where to look or what to achieve. [2]

Deep Learning

Deep learning is almost similar to machine learning but it is a deeper level. The major objective of deep learning is to create a nerve network using the algorithm that can solve the problems it has been given. It is used in particular to solve problems where solutions with traditional methods would require very complex rules or which are very complicated to solve and also very time consuming. Deep learning is used, for example, in identifying or handling speech, images and texts.

II. AREAS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

A. Language Understanding:

The main objective is the capacity to understand and recognize and respond to the natural language. To translate from spoken language to a written form and to translate from

one natural language to another language. Some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Speech Recognition, Computational Linguistics, Question Answering, Information Retrieval, and Language Translation.

B. Learning Systems:

The AI has the Capability to adapt behaviour based on previous experience and to develop general rules concerning the world based on such experience. Some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Cybernetics, Concept Formation.

C. Operation Research Oriented Problem-Solving:

Capacity to formulate a problem in suitable representation, to plan for its solution and to know when new information is needed and how to obtain it. Some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Theorem Proving, Interactive Problem Solving, Automatic Program Writing, and Heuristic Search.

D. Visual Perception:

The new age capability to analyse a sensed scene by relating it to an internal model which represents the perceiving organism's "knowledge of the world." The result of this analysis is a structured set of relationships between entities in the scene. Some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Pattern Recognition, Scene Analysis.

E. Modelling Industry:

The capacity to develop an internal representation and set of transformation rules which can be used to predict the behaviour and relationship between some set of real-world entities. Some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Problem Solving Systems, Modelling Natural Systems, Perceptual and Functional Representations

F. Robotics:

A combination of most or all of the above abilities with the ability to move over terrain and manipulate objects. some of the areas where artificial intelligence is used are Exploration Vehicles, Transportation/Navigation, Industrial Automated Tasks, Security, Agriculture, Marine, Mining, Sanitation, Military, Household

G. Gaming Industry:

The ability to accept a formal set of rules for games such as Chess, Checkers, etc., and to translate these rules into a representation or structure which will allow to solve problem-solving and learning abilities to be used in reaching an adequate level of performance. [5]

III. SOME APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

A. Artificial Neural Network (ANN):

In the power systems the most applications of the artificial neural network are using the multilayer feed forward network. In the neural adaptive PSS, a feed-forward neural network with a single hidden layer is proposed which has two sub networks i.e. adaptive neuro identifier, in which the dynamic characteristics of the plant are tracked and adaptive neuro controller will have to damp the low-frequency oscillations. Radial basis function

network (RBFN) has three layers they are input layers, hidden layers, and output layers. The hidden layer finds centers and widths of the radial basis functions for individual pattern units and the output layer finds the weights between the pattern units and the output units using an unsupervised learning algorithm. A recurrent neural network (RNN) stabilization controller is proposed to improve the transient stability of power systems in which both the governor and AVR is used. The weight of the proposed controller is adjusted on-line. The signal output of the first RNN is added to the PSS signal output for excitation control. The signal output of the second RNN is used as a stabilizing signal for the governor system. ANNs are intelligent controllers to control nonlinear, dynamic systems through learning, which can easily accommodate the nonlinearities and time dependencies. [3]

B. Artificial Intelligence for Medical Image Classification:

Artificial intelligence techniques are used for diagnostic sciences in biomedical image classification. Model-based intelligent analysis and decision-support tools are important in medical imaging for computer-assisted diagnosis and evaluation. [4] CAD helps radiologist who uses the output from a computerized analysis of medical images as a second opinion in detecting lesions, assessing extent of disease, and improving the accuracy and consistency of radiological diagnosis to reduce the rate of false negative cases. [8]

IV. CONCLUSION

The field of artificial intelligence gives the ability to the machines to think analytically, using concepts. Tremendous contribution to the various areas has been made by the Artificial Intelligence techniques from the last 2 decades. Artificial Intelligence will continue to play an increasingly important role in the various fields. This paper is based on the concept of artificial intelligence, areas of artificial intelligence and the artificial intelligence techniques used in the field of Power System Stabilizers (PSS) to maintain system stability and damping of oscillation and provide high-quality performance, in the Network Intrusion Detection to protect the network from intruders, in the medical area in the field of medicine, for medical image classification, in the accounting databases, and described how these AI techniques are used in computer games to solve the common problems and to provide features to the games so as to have fun. There is bright future in the analysis of Network Intrusion Detection and there is also definite future in the area of Power System Stabilizers. We conclude that further research in this area can be done as there are very promising and profitable results that are obtainable from such techniques. While scientists have not yet realized the full potential and ability of artificial intelligence. This technology and its applications will likely have far-reaching effects on human life in the years to come.

REFERENCES

- [1] Holland JH, "Adaptation in Natural and Artificial Systems", 1975.
- [2] C. Sampada,, et al, "Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Intrusion Detection Systems", Proceedings: International Conference on Information Technology: Coding and Computing (ITCC'04),2004.
- [3] Mahdiyeh EslamiI, Hussain Shaareef, Azah Mohamed, "Application of artificial intelligent techniques in PSS design: a survey of the state-of-the-art methods".

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- [4] N Ramesh, C Kambhampati, JRT Monson, PJ Drew, “Artificial intelligence in medicine”, 2004.
- [5] Charles Weddle, Graduate Student, Florida State University “Artificial Intelligence and Computer Games”, unpublished.
- [6] F. D. Laramee, Genetic Algorithms: Evolving the Perfect Troll, AI Game Programming Wisdom, Charles River Media, Inc., Hingham, MA, 2002
- [7] J. Matthews, Basic A* Path finding Made Simple, AI Game Programming Wisdom, Charles River Media, Inc., Hingham, MA, 2002.
- [8] S.N. Deepa, B. Aruna Devi, “A survey on artificial intelligence approaches for medical image classification”, Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol. 4 No. 11 (Nov 2011).